

Effective Defect Prevention Approach in Software Process for Achieving Better Quality Levels

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Abstract—Defect prevention is the most vital but habitually neglected facet of software quality assurance in any project. If functional at all stages of software development, it can condense the time, overheads and wherewithal entailed to engineer a high quality product. The key challenge of an IT industry is to engineer a software product with minimum post deployment defects.

This effort is an analysis based on data obtained for five selected projects from leading software companies of varying software production competence. The main aim of this paper is to provide information on various methods and practices supporting defect detection and prevention leading to thriving software generation. The defect prevention technique unearths 99% of defects. Inspection is found to be an essential technique in generating ideal software generation in factories through enhanced methodologies of abetted and unaided inspection schedules. On an average 13 % to 15% of inspection and 25% - 30% of testing out of whole project effort time is required for 99% - 99.75% of defect elimination.

A comparison of the end results for the five selected projects between the companies is also brought about throwing light on the possibility of a particular company to position itself with an appropriate complementary ratio of inspection testing.

Keywords—Defect Detection and Prevention, Inspections, Software Engineering, Software Process, Testing.

I. INTRODUCTION

A defect in an application can lead to a harmful situation in all phases of software development process. Anything connected to defect is a continual process and not a state. Defect prevention activity stems from comprehension of defects. A defect refers to any inaccuracy or blemish in a software work product or software process. The term defect refers to an error, fault or failure [1]. The IEEE/Standard defines the following terms as Error: a human action that leads to incorrect result.

Fault: incorrect decision taken while understanding the given information, to solve problems or in implementation of process. A Failure: inability of a function to meet the expected requirements [2]–[3].

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Defect prevention [DP] is a process of identifying defects, their root causes and corrective and preventive measures taken to prevent them from recurring in future, thus leading to the production of a quality software product [4]–[5]–[11]–[12]–[15]. Hence, organizations should opt for defect detection and prevention strategies for long-term Return on Investment (ROI).

Among several approaches, inspection has proven to be the most valuable and competent technique in defect detection and prevention [5]–[13]–[14]–[15]. Identified defects are classified at two different points in time 1) time when the defect was first detected and 2) time when defect got fixed. Orthogonal Defect Classification (ODC) is the most prevailing technique for identifying defects wherein defects are grouped into types rather than considered independently. This technique highlights those areas in software development process that require attention [6]–[14].

If a defect dwells for a longer time in the product, it is more expensive to fix it. Therefore, it is necessary to reduce defect injection and boost defect removal efficiency. Defect removal efficiency (DRE) metric quantifies the excellence of the product by computing the number of defects before release of the product to the total number of latent defects [7]–[17].

$$DRE = \frac{\text{number of defects removed during development phase}}{\text{total number of latent defects}}$$

DRE depends upon time and method used to remove defects. But it is always more lucrative for defects to be prevented rather than detected and eliminated.

Certain amount of defects can be prevented through error removal techniques like educating development team through training, by use of formal specifications and formal verifications. It can also be prevented with use of tools, technologies, process and standards. Several tools are available right from requirements phase to maintenance phase to automate the entire development process. Usage of object oriented technology reduces interaction problems thus reducing number of defects arising in these areas. Defects can be prevented with the choice of appropriate process and in compliance with the process. By inculcating quality standards in software development, defects can be prevented to a maximum extent. Root cause analysis for defects is identified to be very successful in prevention of defects in all the booming software companies [8]–[9]–[16].

II. CASE STUDY

The following case studies provide information on various defect detection and prevention techniques that are incorporated in mature companies in delivering a high quality product. This also includes one company that does not strictly adhere to DP strategies.

A. Effective Defect Prevention Techniques Adopted in a Leading Product Based Company in Embedded Systems

The company follows staged process model, which is a representation of CMMI Meta model. The staged process defines five maturity levels and the process areas that are required to achieve a maturity level.

Since 1999-2000, the company follows qualitative and quantitative analysis as a defect preventive strategy. A data base is maintained to capture the mistakes identified after product is shipped to the field. Qualitative analysis comprises of stage kick off meeting to be carried out prior to the start of each life cycle phase or task to highlight those areas where mistakes were committed, identified and actions that were taken for their rectification in the past. Sensitization and discussions are carried out for the current project by handing over the documents of the lessons learned from previous similar type of projects. The core intention is to reduce defect injection and increase defect removal efficiency [10].

In quantitative approach, authentic and realistic data are collected from the stored projects. Based on 80% rule, projects are categorized on platform and technology upon which they were implemented. Control charts are used to inspect for consistency checks at all phases of software development life cycle. If an inspection at a phase exemplifies the non-conformance of the defects in the control band, it reveals the fact that either review was excellent or if review was reprehensible.

Testing comprises of

- Regression testing which ensures non introduction of unintentional behavior or additional errors in the software
- Performance test is conducted to ascertain the performance of requirements.
- Environmental test ensures testing of environment in which the product is to be deployed.
- Health test is also conducted for users of the product in compliance with health safety standards.

The review efficiency metric gives an insight on quality of review conducted. Review efficiency is idyllic if it can identify *one critical defect per every one man hour* spent on reviews.

Review Efficiency = Total number of defects found by reviews / Total number of defects in product

With a review efficiency of 87%, the company reported increasing their productivity from 250 to 400 accentuating the importance of adopting DP strategies. With an inspection-testing time ratio of 15:30, the company was able to reach a quality level of 99.75% defect-free product.

Observation

Inspection is carried out at all phases of software development rather than performing it only at coding stage. Inspection is carried out for requirement specifications, high level design and low level design in addition to code reviews. Company schedules 15% of the total time of the project for inspections and 30% for testing to achieve a quality of 99.75% defect-free product.

As the deployable product is almost free from defects, cost entailed for rework is quite nominal. Since cost of fixing defects after shipment is 10 times more than the cost of fixing it in-house [9], inspection becomes mandatory for highly safety critical systems [11].

Table 1 depicts the estimated time and actual time for 5 different projects. Average time estimated for inspection is 13.9 % of total project time and actual time taken is 14.2%. Test time is estimated to be 28.2% but actual test time is 30.8% of the total project time. Thus for highly critical systems an inspection of 15% and testing of 30% is good enough to achieve nearly 99.75 % of defect-free product.

B. Effective Defect Prevention Techniques Adopted in a Leading Service Based Software Company

The company follows staged continuous model, which is a representation of CMMI Meta model. The continuous process defines five capability levels and process areas that are assessed for five capability levels.

Since 2002, the company is adhering to defect detection and defect prevention techniques to enhance quality of the product. The defect detection techniques are review of plans, schedules, and records. Product and process audits are carried out as part of quality control to uncover defects and correct them. The defect prevention techniques followed in the company includes pro-active, reactive and retrospective DP.

Pro-active DP is to create an environment for controlling defects rather than just reacting to it. A stage kick off meeting is conducted to reveal those areas where slip-ups were committed, recognized and actions taken for their refinement in the past. Company considers from the previous projects, the lessons learnt from the life cycle phases, the DP action items documented and best practices adopted. It leverages from other projects, the DP action items in the organization that are of same nature.

Reactive DP identifies and conducts RCA (Root Cause Analysis) for defects meeting at trigger points or at logical points. Therefore, curative actions are employed along with preventive actions to eliminate the potential defects. The most common root causes for defects identified are lack of communication, lack of training, oversight, project methodology and planning.

Retrospection is performed towards the end of the project or at identified phases to identify strong points and to explore the areas requiring perfection.

Observation

Inspection is executed at all stages of software development. Testing activity includes automation testing, verification and validation testing. From 5 projects listed in

Table 2 it is observed that inspection time estimated is 12.9%, and actual time taken is 14.7% of total project time. With an estimate of 25% of testing time, it is seen that 25.1% of total development time is required to achieve nearly 99% defect-free software product.

The cost of rework for 1% of defect when identified at the customer's site is 10 times the cost required for fixing the same defect when identified in-house [11]. As a matter-of-fact, companies adopting to DP strategies have shown that over a period of time, quality of the product is enhanced while the cost of quality is reduced [12].

C. A company, which is not Strictly Adhering to DP

In comparison with the observations made from previous 2 companies, a company which has not strictly followed DP has also been studied. Because DP is not stringently followed, a substantial amount of time is spent on developer unit testing, verification and validation.

Observation

The company schedules 5% of total project time for inspection which necessitates almost 40% of testing time out of the total development effort. Defects that can be captured with this ratio of inspection and testing are only 80%.

Cost required for rework is found to be more expensive than the cost incurred in adhering to DP strategies. Of the selected 5 projects, it is observed from the Table III that with an estimated inspection time of 4.8%, actual taken time taken for inspection is 5.5%. This ratio requires a scrupulous testing of 40.6% of actual time against an estimated time of 34.5% out of whole project time. If inspection time is increased in all phases of software development life cycle, then testing time gets significantly reduced.

Fig. 1 shows a comparative graph of inspection and testing for 5 selected projects from 3 different companies. From the graph, it is clear that with increase in inspection time, testing time gets decreased, as most of the defects get uncovered during inspection. Investment in inspection is initially high but over a period of time it becomes stable, which means cost is reduced and quality is increased.

Fig. 1 Comparative graphs of inspection and testing for 3 companies over 5 selected projects

III. CONCLUSION

Implementation of defect prevention strategy not only reflects a high level of process maturity but is also a most valuable investment. The detection of errors in development life cycle helps to prevent the passage of errors from requirement specification to design and from design to code. Analysis carried out across three companies shows the importance of incorporating defect prevention techniques in delivering a high quality product. The focal point of quality cost investment is to invest in right DP activities rather than investing in rework which is seen as an outcome of uncaptured defects. There are several methods, techniques and practices for defect prevention. Software inspection has proved to be the most successful defect detection and prevention technique. The goal of reaching a consistently 99 % defect-free software depends much on effective defect prevention techniques adopted.

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TABLE I
TIME AND DEFECT PROFILE OF A LEADING SOFTWARE PRODUCT BASED COMPANY

	P1		P2		P3		P4		P5	
Total time (in man hours)	250	263	200	201	340	355	170	167	100	101
Req time	20	23	30	35	25	23	15	14	23	25
Req review	2	1	5	6	3	3	2	1	2	2
Req test	5	6	8	8	5	6	5	7	4	5
Design time	35	40	80	82	45	46	28	29	40	46
Design review	3	3	10	14	6	5	5	3	5	5
Design test	9	11	20	22	9	10	8	10	8	11
Implementation time	90	100	200	201	115	118	52	50	100	101
Code review	15	16	26	27	15	17	9	7	15	17
Testing	78	81	64	66	90	93	60	68	50	58
Insp Avg	10	9.3	23.7	29	14	13.7	10	6.3	12	12.7
Test Avg	30.7	32.7	30.7	32	34.7	36.3	24.3	28.3	20.7	24.7

Shaded column indicates estimated values and unshaded columns indicate the actual values
Req – Requirement, Insp – Inspection, Avg – Average

TABLE II
 TIME AND DEFECT PROFILE OF A LEADING SERVICE BASED COMPANY

	P1		P2		P3		P4		P5	
Total time (in man hours)	250	263	502	507	340	368	166	167	255	263
Req time	25	20	50	55	32	32	10	12	25	20
Req review	4	5	10	12	12	13	5	7	6	7
Req test	4	4	10	9	12	10	5	5	7	3
Design time	40	45	100	110	40	45	20	22	40	45
Design review	6	6	18	20	17	19	8	11	8	9
Design test	7	8	19	17	18	12	10	10	9	8
Implementation time	85	100	180	165	100	105	45	40	85	100
Code review	12	13	32	34	31	35	13	14	12	15
Testing	55	56	63	68	61	65	45	50	50	52
Avg insp	7.3	8	20	22	20	22.3	8.7	10.7	8.7	10.3
Avg test	22	23	30.7	31.3	30.3	29	20	21.7	22	21

TABLE III
 TIME AND DEFECT PROFILE OF A COMPANY NOT STRINGENT TO DP

	P1		P2		P3		P4		P5	
Total time (in man hours)	225	230	490	507	340	368	150	159	240	250
Req time	20	24	54	55	28	30	15	19	30	30
Req review	2	2	3	4	3	3	1	1	2	2
Testing	9	10	20	22	16	16	6	7	10	11
Design time	30	35	70	77	40	42	30	33	45	45
Design review	3	4	4	5	3	3	1	1	2	3
Testing	11	12	26	28	17	18	9	10	13	17
Implementation time	85	100	180	165	100	105	45	40	85	100
Code review	6	6	13	13	12	13	9	10	12	12
Testing	68	80	120	133	93	105	50	68	65	72
Avg insp	3.7	4	6.7	7.3	6	6.3	3.7	4	4	5.7
Avg test	29	34	55.3	61	42	46.3	21.7	28.3	29.3	33.3